

Polymeric membranes functionalized with deep eutectic solvents as separators in microbial fuel cells

K. Hamalová^a, S. Sánchez Segado^b, V.M. Ortiz-Martínez^{b,*}, M.J. Salar-García^{c,**}

^a Centre for Nanomaterials and Biotechnology, Faculty of Science, Jan Evangelista Purkyně University in Ústí nad Labem, 400 96, Ústí nad Labem, Czech Republic

^b Department of Chemical and Environmental Engineering, Technical University of Cartagena (UPCT), Campus Muralla Del Mar, 30202, Cartagena, Spain

^c Department of Chemical and Environmental Engineering, Technical University of Cartagena (UPCT), Campus Alfonso XIII, Aulario C, 30203, Cartagena, Spain

HIGHLIGHTS

- Use of deep eutectic solvents (DES) as active phases in MFC membranes.
- DES based on Aliquat-336 and menthol were tested with PVC at varying ratios.
- Membranes with 50 % DES achieved a power density of 292.2 mW m⁻³.
- COD removal improved to 78.3 % with membranes containing 50 % DES.

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ABSTRACT

This study explores novel membranes based on deep eutectic solvents (DES) combined with commercial polyvinyl chloride (PVC) for bioenergy generation in microbial fuel cells (MFCs) utilizing wastewater. The incorporation of DES into these systems provides a cost-effective and environmentally sustainable approach for fabricating exchange membranes, thanks to their unique properties, including ionic conductivity, solvation capabilities, ease of fabrication, and biodegradability. Polymer membranes were synthesized using a solution casting technique, incorporating a DES composed of Aliquat-336 (trioctylmethylammonium chloride) and menthol in a 1:1 M ratio. The final membrane compositions included the eutectic phase at percentages of 30 %, 50 %, and 70 %, which were compared to pristine PVC membranes. Characterization techniques such as scanning electron microscopy (SEM), energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDX), ionic exchange capacity (IEC), ion transport number, water uptake and swelling ratio were employed to assess membrane properties. This study focuses on MFCs used for wastewater treatment and energy recovery, highlighting the potential of DES-based membranes as a more sustainable alternative to traditional materials and establishing a new avenue for the use of DES in bioelectrochemical applications. Specifically, the membranes containing 50 % DES exhibited promising performance, demonstrating the potential of DES as an active phase in membrane technology, with a power density of 292.2 mW m⁻³ and a COD removal rate of 78.3 %.

1. Introduction

In the context of the global energy crisis and the urgent need for effective wastewater treatment, microbial fuel cells (MFCs) present a promising solution [1]. MFCs have the unique ability to generate electricity through bacterial metabolism, using organic substrates as fuel sources. This dual functionality allows MFCs to not only produce

sustainable energy but also treat wastewater simultaneously [2]. Many studies have demonstrated the technical feasibility of MFCs, sparking enthusiasm within the scientific community for their potential as a green energy source and efficient wastewater treatment technology [3]. In general, the devices have shown potential in several key applications such as urban and industrial wastewater treatment [4,5], power generation in remote areas for sensors [6], biomass utilization for renewable

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* Corresponding author.

** Corresponding author.

E-mail addresses: katerina.hamalova@ujep.cz (K. Hamalová), victor.ortiz@upct.es (V.M. Ortiz-Martínez), mariajose.salar@upct.es (M.J. Salar-García).

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energy production [7], and contamination removal in groundwater [8]. Furthermore, new modified versions of the original MFC technology architecture have been proposed in order to expand its application into additional fields [9].

Membranes play a critical role in the performance of MFCs by facilitating ion exchange while separating the anode and cathode compartments [10]. The efficiency of these membranes directly impacts the overall power output and operational stability of MFCs. Deep eutectic solvents (DESs) have emerged as promising alternatives to organic solvents in various application fields, especially in separation and extraction processes [11] but increasingly in electrochemical applications [12], including sensing [13], flow batteries [14] and supercapacitors [15]. Regarding the first mentioned field, DESs have been utilized in various electrochemical systems, primarily serving as liquid electrolytes. For instance, DESs have been employed in electrodeposition processes, offering a non-conventional medium for metal deposition [16]. Additionally, DESs have been explored as green electrolytes in batteries, capacitors and supercapacitors, providing environmentally benign alternatives to traditional solvents [17,18]. In bioelectrochemical systems, DESs have been applied in biosensor development, enhancing the performance and stability of the sensors [19]. These applications demonstrate the versatility of DESs in electrochemical and bioelectrochemical systems, primarily in their liquid form. In contrast, this study aims to demonstrate the benefits of incorporating DES phases into polymer membranes.

These compounds can be considered closely akin to ionic liquids (ILs), with shared properties such as high tunability, ion conductivity, and low volatility, but offer additional benefits, including lower toxicity, biodegradability, and ease of preparation [20]. Incorporating DESs into membrane materials can potentially enhance the performance of MFCs by improving ion transport and membrane stability. DESs are typically composed of a mixture of a hydrogen bond donor (HBD) and a hydrogen bond acceptor (HBA), resulting in a eutectic mixture with unique physicochemical properties. These solvents exhibit high thermal and chemical stability, tunable viscosity, and low environmental impact.

Conventional proton exchange membranes for MFCs such as Nafion® and its derivatives, based on sulfonated polytetrafluoroethylene (PTFE), have been widely used in electrochemical applications due to their good conductivity, chemical stability, and well-established performance in demanding environments [21]. Despite their extensive use and proven success, these membranes face some limitations. The high cost of Nafion® and similar materials, often associated with their complex manufacturing processes, restricts their widespread adoption, particularly in large-scale industrial applications, reducing the chance of commercialization of MFC. In response, alternative membranes made from materials such as polyvinyl alcohol (PVA), polyvinylidene fluoride (PVDF), sulfonated poly ether ether ketone (SPEEK), clays and ceramics, among others, have been developed for MFC applications. These alternatives aim to address the limitations of conventional membranes by offering more cost-effective options while maintaining or enhancing performance in MFC systems [21]. The economic analysis of DES highlighted a substantial cost advantage over Nafion®, with prices ranging from €7 to €100 per kilogram, depending on their primary components, making them a more affordable alternative [22].

Recent studies have begun to explore the incorporation of deep eutectic solvents (DES) into polymeric membranes, focusing on their potential to improve membrane properties for specific electrochemical applications, particularly in MFCs used for wastewater treatment and energy recovery. DES-based membranes would ideally offer high ionic conductivity and reduced ohmic resistance, all of which could be crucial for optimizing MFC performance. The unique properties of DES, such as their hydrogen bonding capabilities, viscosity, and ability to solvate a wide range of ions, can potentially contribute to improving the ionic conductivity of the membranes. For example, Rahman et al. [23] demonstrated that poly(vinyl alcohol) (PVA) membranes immersed in DESs exhibited conductivity ranging from $2.78 \cdot 10^{-6}$ to $2.27 \cdot 10^{-2}$ S

cm^{-1} , depending on the molar ratio of the components. This improvement in conductivity suggests that DES can enhance transport efficiency in MFCs. Additionally, DES-based membranes need to be studied in terms of water uptake, which could help maintain their structural integrity, ensuring they can withstand the harsh conditions of wastewater treatment systems while potentially maintaining their conductivity over time. Wong et al. [24] found that chitosan/carboxymethyl cellulose membranes with choline chloride/urea DES (1:2) exhibited proton conductivity up to $1.57 \cdot 10^{-2}$ S cm^{-1} , comparable to the standard Nafion®-117 membrane. The promising characteristics of DES-based membranes highlight their suitability for MFC applications, offering a more sustainable and cost-effective alternative to traditional materials as separators in MFCs.

While ILs have been widely studied as electrolyte membranes in MFCs over the last years [25,26], the present study represents pioneering research in studying membranes based on DES for MFC devices. In this work, novel DES-based membranes composed of trioctylmethylammonium chloride (Aliquat 336) as HBA and menthol as HBD were studied. The phase Aliquat 336-menthol is relatively insoluble, providing a stable and sustainable alternative for membrane fabrication. Menthol is an environmentally friendly component derived from renewable resources [27], further enhancing the green properties of the resulting membranes. Moreover, Aliquat 336 is utilized in ion-exchange membranes due to its robust quaternary ammonium structure. It offers excellent chemical stability and compatibility with polymer matrices, enhancing membrane durability [28]. PVC is employed as the polymeric matrix for the DES phase, offering mechanical strength, chemical resistance, and ease of processing, making it a robust choice for membrane applications. Moreover, the simple casting method enables efficient and scalable fabrication, ensuring uniform distribution of the active components [29].

Thus, this work explores the synthesis, characterization, and evaluation of various membrane compositions cast at different ratios of PVC and a eutectic phase based on Aliquat 336-menthol. These membranes were investigated in single-chamber MFCs using real industrial wastewater as the feedstock. The performances of the membranes were analyzed based on their electrical production capacity and efficiency in wastewater treatment in terms of chemical oxygen demand removal. This approach is intended to showcase for the first time the potential of DES-based membranes in the field of MFCs.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Membrane preparation

Polymer membranes based on commercial PVC and the lab-made DES were prepared using a solution casting technique. The DES consisted of Aliquat-336 (trioctylmethylammonium chloride) and menthol at a 1:1 M ratio. For its synthesis, equimolar amounts of Aliquat-336 and menthol were combined, and the mixture was gently heated while stirring continuously until a clear, homogeneous liquid was formed. The final compositions of the membranes were 100 % PVC, 70 % PVC - 30 % DES, 50 % PVC - 50 % DES, and 30 % PVC - 70 % DES. These ratios were selected based on the need for a balance between synthesis feasibility, stability, and expected electrochemical performance. The PVC content ensures structural integrity and ease of processing, while the DES phases act as plasticizers, enhancing ion conductivity. The varying DES ratios allow for an investigation of different mechanical properties and electrochemical behaviors, optimizing membrane conductivity and stability. For the casting process, PVC and the DES were dissolved in THF (tetrahydrofuran) and stirred with a magnetic stirrer until a homogeneous solution was obtained. The resulting solution was then poured into a 28 mm diameter borosilicate glass ring and left to evaporate overnight to ensure the solvent was completely removed.

2.2. Membrane characterization

2.2.1. Morphological and elemental studies

The composition and morphology of the synthesized membranes were comprehensively analyzed using scanning electron microscopy with energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy techniques (SEM-EDX). Specifically, a Hitachi S3500N scanning electron microscope, equipped with an « X-Flash 5010 » Bruker AXS microanalysis system for EDX analysis and elemental mapping, was employed. This analytical approach allowed for detailed examination of the morphological characteristics, such as surface appearance as well as the determination of the overall chemical composition and the spatial distribution of elements within the membrane configurations under investigation. Finally, membrane thickness was measured with a digital micrometer.

2.2.2. Water uptake analysis and swelling ratio

The analysis of water uptake of the synthesized membranes was conducted by comparing the initial dry weight and the wet weights after immersion. Initially, the membranes were weighed in their dry state and then submerged in 50 mL of distilled water for 24 h at room temperature. After this period, the membranes were removed, and excess surface water was gently blotted with absorbent paper to determine the wet weight. The percentage of water absorption was then calculated according to equation (1):

$$\text{Water uptake (\%)} = \frac{W_w - W_d}{W_d} \times 100 \quad (1)$$

where W_w represents the weight after water immersion, and W_d is the initial dry weight [30,31].

The swelling ratio (SR) was determined by measuring the thickness of the membranes before and after being soaked in distilled water. To this goal, the membranes were cut and immersed in distilled water for 24 h. After the soaking period, the samples were taken out, excess surface water was removed using absorbent paper and the thickness of the wet membranes (T_w) was measured and compared with the thickness of the dry membranes (T_d). The following equation (2) was used to determine the swelling ratio [32]:

$$\text{SR} = \frac{T_w - T_d}{T_d} \times 100 \quad (2)$$

2.2.3. Ion exchange capacity (IEC)

The ion exchange capacity (IEC) of the prepared membranes was determined through titration. First, the membranes were converted to their protonic form by soaking them in a 1 M HCl solution for 24 h. After this, the membranes were thoroughly rinsed with distilled water to eliminate any residual acid. Following this preparation, the membranes were titrated with a 0.01 M NaOH solution. The IEC was calculated using equation (3):

$$\text{IEC (m equiv / g dry membrane)} = \frac{V_{\text{NaOH}} \cdot M_{\text{NaOH}}}{m} \times 1000 \quad (3)$$

where V_{NaOH} is the volume of NaOH consumed in the titration, M_{NaOH} is the molarity of the NaOH solution used and m is the mass of the dry membrane (g) [30,31].

2.2.4. Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS)

The conductivity of the membranes was determined using Electrochemical Impedance Spectroscopy (EIS). The membranes were placed between two electrodes and frequency response analysis (FRA) was carried out. Internal resistance values were derived from Nyquist plots, which were obtained through the AC Impedance Spectroscopy method using an Autolab PGSTAT302N (Metrohm Autolab B.V., Utrecht, The Netherlands). Electrical impedance measurements covered a range from 1 MHz to 0.1 Hz with a perturbation voltage amplitude of 0.05 V. All measurements were conducted at a constant temperature of 25 °C. The

ionic conductivities of the membranes were calculated by equation (4):

$$\sigma = \frac{L}{A \cdot R} \times 100 \quad (4)$$

where σ is the ionic conductivity ($\text{S} \cdot \text{cm}^{-1}$), L is the membrane thickness (cm), A is the cross-sectional area (cm^2), and R is the resistance (Ω) of the membranes given by the Nyquist plots [33,34].

2.2.5. Chronoamperometry

The total ionic transport number (t_{ion}) of the membranes was determined through the Wagner equation (5) by chronoamperometry (Autolab PGSTAT302N, Metrohm Autolab B.V., Utrecht, The Netherlands) applying 0.5 V [35]:

$$t_{\text{ion}} = \frac{I_0 - I_e}{I_0} \times 100 \quad (5)$$

Where I_0 and I_e are the current intensity at time zero and the current intensity at the end of the chronoamperometry (I vs t), respectively. This parameter gives the percentage of the ionic current over the total current.

2.3. MFC set up and recording data

Single-chamber MFC systems (Schott Duran glass reactors) were used to evaluate the performance of the membranes. The reactors underwent a 7-day maturation phase prior to a 20-day monitoring period. Each MFC was filled with 150 mL of a mixture consisting of 80 % industrial wastewater and 20 % sludge (v/v), both sourced from the primary treatment stage of a local fine chemical industry. This was followed by a 2-h open-circuit voltage (OCV) phase to promote initial biofilm formation. Afterward, an external resistance was applied and progressively decreased to stimulate further biofilm development. To maintain nutrient availability, 50 mL of wastewater was replaced every two days during the maturation phase. At the end of this period, the anolyte was removed and replaced with 150 mL of fresh 80/20 %v/v wastewater-sludge mixture, marking the beginning of the 20-day operational phase. The initial chemical oxygen demand (COD) in the anode chamber was 3188 mg L^{-1} , with a pH of 6.8, prior to the 20-day monitoring period.

The anode consisted of irregularly shaped porous graphite granules (≈ 0.3 cm diameter, 100 g) and an 18 mm graphite rod to facilitate electron conduction from organic matter digestion to the external circuit. The cathode was composed of carbon cloth sprayed with carbon-supported platinum at a load density of 0.4 g Pt- $\text{cm}_{\text{cathode}}^{-2}$. Synthesized membranes were positioned between the anode chamber and carbon cloth cathodes, secured using rubber gaskets and 28 mm rounded metal joint clips.

The MFCs operated in batch mode for 20 days with the voltage monitored using a Picolog data acquisition system (Pico Technology, UK). Experiments were run in duplicate, and polarization tests were conducted via linear sweep voltammetry using Autolab equipment, varying the external voltage from open-circuit voltage to 0.05 V at a scan rate of 0.25 mV s^{-1} . Polarization and power curves were plotted to analyze the voltage output and determine the maximum power density. Internal resistance (R_{int}) of the MFCs was calculated from maximum power density, and the external resistance load was adjusted to promote optimal biofilm development during the initial maturation phase.

COD removal efficiency was monitored using a photometric method based on COD tests (Merck Millipore) according to equation (6):

$$\text{COD removal (\%)} = \frac{\text{COD}_0 - \text{COD}_f}{\text{COD}_0} \times 100 \quad (6)$$

where COD_0 represents the initial COD load of the wastewater and COD_f is the final value of the COD load after a certain time.

Normalized energy recovery (NER) in $\text{kWh} \cdot \text{m}^{-3}$ was calculated

according to equation (7) to calculate the conversion of organic compounds to energy [36]:

$$\text{NER} = \frac{\text{power} \times \text{time}}{\text{removed COD (within time t)}} \times 100 \quad (7)$$

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Morphological and elemental studies

The surface morphology of the membranes was analyzed using SEM, as presented in Fig. 1A–D. All samples exhibit flat, smooth, and homogeneous surfaces, which are characteristic of PVC-based membranes. No evidence of cracks, pores, or phase separation is observed in any of the membranes. The surface integrity suggests that the incorporation of DES at various concentrations does not compromise the structural uniformity of the material. In Fig. 1D, a few minor exogenous particles can be seen, likely introduced during manual handling and sample mounting for SEM imaging. These do not reflect inherent defects in the membrane

Fig. 1. Photos of synthesized membranes (top image) and SEM-EDX analysis: A, A') PVC; B, B') 30 % DES; C, C') 50 % DES and D, D') 70 % DES.

structure. Overall, the SEM micrographs confirm that the surface morphology remains consistent across pristine and DES-modified membranes, supporting the stability of the fabrication process. However, an increase in the amount of DES added results in an increase in the flexibility of the membranes. Specifically, membranes containing 70 % DES are the most flexible, while membranes containing only PVC are clearly rigid. It was also observed that regardless of the amount of DES, all membranes were colorless.

The spectra of the EDX analysis of the different membranes are shown in Fig. 1A', B', C' and D'. In all images, chloride peaks associated with the composition of the polymer matrix were observed. Additional nitrogen and oxygen peaks appeared in the spectra of membranes containing DES, all of which are associated with the structure of the eutectic phase.

The results of the elemental mapping analysis are in line with the SEM-EDX results. As shown in Fig. 2, the membranes exhibit a homogeneous surface with a uniform distribution of all representative elements from both PVC and DES. A homogeneous surface with a uniform distribution of all components ensures that all regions of the membrane exhibit similar properties for uniform performance, indicates the absence of irregularities and suggests the absence of regions of incompatibility between the PVC and the DES phase, which would also be beneficial for long-term stability. On the other hand, differences in terms of color density and intensity can be appreciated in the SEM images between the bare PVC and the rest of the DES functionalized membranes.

3.2. Water uptake and swelling ratio

The water uptake capacity of pure PVC membrane is low (0.21 %) as compared to the membranes containing DES. This result is caused by the strong hydrophobicity of the polymeric groups present in its structure. However, the water uptake is observed to increase as the amount of DES also increases, probably caused by the formation of hydrogen bonds with the -OH group of menthol which promotes water retention. In the case of membranes containing 30 % DES, the water uptake was still low (1.9 %). However, in the membranes containing higher amounts of DES, a loss of weight was observed, which might be caused by the leakage of the DES. Specifically, the membranes containing 50 % DES show a loss of weight of 0.5 % after 24 h immersed in water whereas the membranes containing 70 % DES show a loss of weight of 19 %. These results might be caused by the high amount of DES and the low amount of polymer in the structure.

The water uptake values of reference membranes, such as Nafion®-117 (with a thickness of 175 μm), are reported to be 18 % [37]. Other well-known membranes, such as sulfonated polybenzimidazole (spBI) and sulfonated poly(ether ether ketone) (SPEEK), show a wide range of water uptake values, typically from 20 % to 50 %, depending on the blending or functionalization materials used [38]. As observed, the DES membranes reported here exhibit lower water uptake. While higher water uptake generally improves ion conductivity in MFC membranes, excessive water absorption can lead to dimensional instability and degradation of the membrane's structural properties, which can negatively impact its performance [39].

Regarding the swelling ratio, the results are shown in Table 1. In all cases, the swelling ratio was lower than 11 %, with the maximum value observed for the membrane containing 70 % of DES (10.2 %) and the minimum for the bare PVC membrane (4.5 %). Despite the low values obtained for this parameter in all cases, the results show that an increase in the DES content increases the swelling ratio.

3.3. Ion-exchange capacity

The ion-exchange capacity (IEC) is one of the most critical metrics for assessing proton-exchange membranes. The addition of DES improves the IEC of the PVC-based membranes reaching values over $0.60 \text{ eq} \cdot \text{g}^{-1}$ in

Fig. 2. Elemental mapping images of synthesized membranes: A) PVC; B) 30 % DES; C) 50 % DES and D) 70 % DES.

Table 1
Swelling ratio of the membranes.

Membrane	Swelling ratio (%)
PVC	4.5
30 % DES	7.7
50 % DES	8.6
70 % DES	10.2

all cases. A maximum IEC of $0.69 \text{ meq}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$ is achieved at 50 % DES loading; both 30 % and 70 % DES formulations plateau around $0.66 \text{ meq}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$, indicating a saturation threshold beyond which additional DES may contribute more to clustering than to new ion-exchange sites. Regardless of the amount of DES, the IEC of functionalized membranes was higher than that exhibited by bare PVC-based membranes, with reported values of $0.024 \text{ meq}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$ [31,40]. The reported IEC for reference membranes like Nafion®-117 is $0.92 \text{ meq}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$ [37]. Although the PVC-DES membranes exhibit lower values of IEC, they remain within a competitive range and offer distinct advantages: the intrinsic

hydrophobicity of PVC keeps swelling low (4.5 % for pure PVC, up to ~10 % at highest DES loading), thereby preserving dimensional stability and mechanical integrity under MFC operating conditions. By balancing moderate IEC enhancements with low swelling, these DES-functionalized PVC membranes emerge as promising and cost-effective membranes for MFC applications.

3.4. Electrochemical Impedance Spectroscopy

Fig. 3 shows the Nyquist plots obtained from the IES performed on membranes functionalized with DES. As observed, there is a noticeable difference in the ohmic resistance recorded for the different samples, with a decreasing trend as the DES content increases. This behavior indicates that the incorporation of DES significantly influences the ionic transport properties of the membranes. The Nyquist plots for all three membranes exhibit a similar pattern, which consists of a semicircle (total or partial) in the high-frequency region and an inclined line in the low-frequency region. This response is characteristic of Warburg-type behavior, commonly seen in fuel cells, and reflects the diffusion of ionic species into the electrode material. Specifically, membranes containing 30 % DES display a complete semicircle in the high-frequency region. However, as the DES content increases, the semicircle becomes increasingly partial, with the membrane containing 70 % DES showing the shortest semicircle. This observation suggests a reduction in resistance related to ionic transport as the DES concentration rises.

Table 2 provides a detailed summary of the resistances extracted from the Nyquist plots alongside the calculated ionic conductivities and membrane thicknesses. The results show a clear trend where the resistance of the membranes decreases as the DES content increases: 30 % DES > 50 % DES > 70 % DES. The membrane with 70 % DES exhibits the lowest resistance, 676 Ω , which is 2.2 times lower than that of the membrane containing 30 % DES (1500 Ω). Regarding ionic conductivity, a similar trend is observed, with the highest value of 0.0376 mS cm^{-1} being recorded for the membrane containing 70 % DES. This increase in conductivity correlates with the ionic mobility facilitated by the higher DES content. When these findings are considered in conjunction with the water uptake results discussed earlier, a clear relationship emerges. The water uptake capacity increases with DES content, which likely contributes to the improved ionic conductivity. This can be attributed to the hydrogen bonding interactions between water molecules and the -OH group in menthol, present in the DES. However, the membranes with higher DES content (50 % and 70 %) also exhibit some weight loss during water uptake measurements, likely due to the leaching of DES. Despite this, the membranes at 50 % of DES retain sufficient DES to promote ionic transport, as reflected in their reduced resistance and

Fig. 3. Nyquist plot obtained from the IES measurement of the membranes functionalized with DES.

Table 2

Bulk resistance and ionic conductivity of the membranes functionalized with DES.

Membrane	Resistance (Ω)	Average Thickness (μm)	Ionic Conductivity (mS cm^{-1})
30 % DES	1500	149	$9.96 \cdot 10^{-3}$
50 % DES	1000	352	$3.52 \cdot 10^{-2}$
70 % DES	676	254	$3.76 \cdot 10^{-2}$

increased ionic conductivity.

The values of conductivities displayed in Table 2 are comparable to those exhibited by previously reported PVC-based membranes functionalized with ionic liquids containing methyltrioctylammonium chloride or Aliquat 336 [33]. For its part, Nafion®-117 typically exhibits higher conductivities, ranging from 10^{-1} to 10^{-2} S cm^{-1} , depending on the hydration and temperature conditions [41,42]. Further optimization of DES membranes through compositional adjustments could enhance their competitiveness. In these membranes, PVC serves as a non-conductive support, while the DES serves as a functionalizing agent. Other DES phases and membrane manufacturing methods could further improve their conductivity in future studies.

3.5. Chronoamperometry

The percentage of the ionic transport number of the membranes is shown in Fig. 4. As can be observed, the ionic transport number increases as the content of DES also increases reaching the maximum value for membranes containing 70 % of DES (92.99 %). The values plotted in Fig. 4 demonstrate that the addition of DES such as Aliquat 336:menthol to a PVC matrix results in an increase in the ionic conductivity of the membranes. These results are in line with those exhibited by PVC membranes containing ionic liquids based on trioctylmethylammonium chloride [35].

3.6. Microbial fuel cell analysis

The MFCs operating with the different membranes elaborated were run in batch mode for 20 days. The systems were polarized on day 5, 12, and 19 (see Fig. 5). The polarization curves after 5 days (Fig. 5A) show significant differences between the curves of the systems working with membranes functionalized with DES and those working with bare PVC membranes. In this case, the curve appears more linear, and it shows a higher slope in the ohmic and mass transfer regions. Regarding the power curves, they show that MFCs using any DES-containing membrane exhibit higher power densities than those systems working with bare PVC membranes. In particular, the maximum power density was achieved with membranes containing 50 % DES (292.2 mW m^{-3}) followed by the membrane containing 70 % DES (265.7 mW m^{-3}) and the

Fig. 4. Percentage of the ionic transport number of the membranes.

Fig. 5. Polarization and power curves of the MFC working with the different membranes elaborated after 5 days (A, B), 12 days (C, D), and 19 days (E, F).

membranes containing 30 % DES (222.1 mW m^{-3}). These findings align with the earlier results on bulk resistance and ionic conductivity, as the membrane containing 50 % DES exhibited the highest ionic conductivity, translating to greater power output. While these membranes do not yet reach the efficiency of Nafion®, which has been reported to achieve a power density of 600 mW m^{-3} in the same systems with a similar wastewater source [35,43], they still demonstrate a significant level of performance. This highlights a promising new pathway for optimizing DES-based membranes, offering substantial potential for further enhancement of their electrochemical properties and efficiency in practical applications.

The behavior of the polarization curves of the MFC integrated with DES-based membranes over time tended to unify whereas the systems working with the bare PVC membranes showed worse results (see Fig. 5C–E, and G). In this case, an increase in the slope of the polarization curve is observed and a reduction in the current until values below 0.3 A m^{-3} . In addition, after 20 days of operating the maximum power density output reached a minimum value of 35.1 mW m^{-3} , which is

62.2% lower than the value obtained after 4 days. Regardless of the DES content, the maximum power density obtained using the functionalized PVC membranes is higher than that achieved using PVC membranes containing 70 % of the ionic liquid Aliquat 336 [33]. These results demonstrate the enhanced stability and performance of DES-based membranes in MFCs.

Fig. 6 shows the energy recovery per unit of volume over time. As can be observed, the longest operating condition has the highest energy recovery for all membranes studied, which is in agreement with the nature of the MFC technology. Moreover, the addition of DES to the membrane structure has a positive effect on the NER, as a higher DES content leads to a higher NER. MFC working with membranes containing 50 % and 70 % DES show the maximum NER after 456 h of operating time (0.13 kW h m^{-3}) whereas membranes containing 30 % of DES allow MFC to reach a maximum value of 0.12 kW h m^{-3} . In all cases, the NER of MFCs operating with DES-based membranes overcomes the values obtained by MFCs working with bare PVC membranes. The results obtained are in good agreement with those reported elsewhere

Fig. 6. Energy recovery of the MFCs over time.

[44].

Regarding the evolution of the continuous power density output by the systems (Fig. 7), an increase in this parameter over time was observed when the MFCs incorporated DES-functionalized membranes. After 12 days of operation, the MFCs incorporating eutectic phases reached a stable power response. As shown, the MFCs equipped with the membranes containing 50 % DES delivered the highest power output after approximately 150 h of operation. It is worth noting that the external loads of the MFCs were adjusted in accordance with the optimal resistance determined from polarization tests, since maximum power is achieved when the internal resistance of the systems equals the external load of the cell. Thus, external resistance was fixed in each case to ensure optimal operating conditions. In light of these results, 30 % DES appears to be below the optimal content, while 70 % DES implies that the membrane loses active phase since there is not enough polymer to support the eutectic phase, resulting in poorer outcomes compared to the intermediate composition. Clearly, the MFC with the pristine PVC membrane set as control delivered significantly lower power densities than the DES-based membranes tested. Towards the end of the experimental period, a decrease in power density was observed, attributed to the depletion of organic matter at the anode.

In terms of wastewater treatment capacity, the incorporation of DES into the PVC-membrane structure enhances COD removal. After 5 days, the MFCs working with membranes containing 30 % DES reached 73.3 % COD removal whereas membranes containing 50 % DES reached up to 78.3 % (see Fig. 8). By contrast, MFCs using bare PVC-membranes exhibited the lowest COD removal (27.7 %), similar to that observed for membranes containing 70 % DES. These results are consistent with the previously observed power density trends. The addition of DES as an active component in the membrane structure improves the MFC in terms of both power output and wastewater treatment capacity. In particular, the addition of 30 % DES to the PVC-membrane structure results in a 2.4-

Fig. 7. Evolution of the power output over time of the MFCs working with the PVC and DES-based membranes.

Fig. 8. COD removal of the MFCs working with the different PVC and DES-based membranes.

fold increase in COD removal compared to the bare PVC-membranes. The significant difference in COD removal observed in the 70 % DES condition compared to other modifications can be attributed to the structural instability of the membranes at high DES content. At 70 % DES, the excessive amount of DES within the membrane matrix likely leads to its leakage into the surrounding environment, as previously observed in the water uptake tests.

These findings highlight the dual role of DES in improving ionic conductivity and wastewater treatment efficiency while emphasizing the need for optimal DES content. Excessive DES compromises membrane stability and overall performance, demonstrating the importance of balancing DES levels in the membrane structure.

4. Conclusions

This study demonstrates the effectiveness of using deep eutectic solvents (DES) as active phases in polyvinyl chloride (PVC) membranes for microbial fuel cells (MFCs) enhancing both power density and wastewater treatment capacity. Throughout a 20-day operation period in batch mode, MFCs equipped with DES-functionalized membranes clearly outperformed those with bare PVC membranes. The optimal DES content was found to be 50 % compared to 30 % and 70 % compositions. Membranes containing 50 % DES achieved the highest power density of 292.2 mW m^{-2} and maintained stable performance after 12 days. In terms of chemical oxygen demand removal, membranes with 50 % DES achieved a remarkable 78.3 % reduction, compared to just 27.7 % for bare PVC membranes. Meanwhile, the 30 % DES composition also showed significant improvements, although the 70 % DES composition led to diminished performance, likely due to insufficient polymer content to support the eutectic phase. These results suggest the addition of DES can be an effective way to functionalize ion exchange membranes in MFCs, although the content of DES must be balanced since excessive amounts may lead to issues such as leakage, affecting both power output and treatment efficiency. Overall, this work underscores the potential of DES as a viable active component in MFC membrane technology, establishing a new avenue for research. Future work should approach the broad range of available DES and investigate the optimal molar compositions of their components to further enhance membrane performance in MFCs.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

K. Hamalová: Investigation. S. Sánchez Segado: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft. V.M. Ortiz-Martínez: Writing – review

& editing, Writing – original draft, Supervision, Project administration, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **M.J. Salar-García:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Supervision, Project administration, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpowsour.2025.237388>.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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